

ESTIMATING A PREDICTION MODEL FOR SHARE PRICE BASED ON THE INFLUENCE OF THE BOARD ATTRIBUTES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract. Share price plays an important role in determining a firm's value.

However, existing studies mainly focus on the role of the organizational bottom line in influencing the share price. Also, these studies lack empirical studies. This study therefore explores the effects of the board of directors on the share price of the 153 publicly traded companies in Nigeria examined for 10 years (2014-2023). Board attributes are proxied in this paper by board gender diversity, board independence, and board size. The share price is the closing share price at the year's end. A mixed method of quantitative analysis was employed using a panel regression model. After accounting for diagnostic tests, the findings show that board gender diversity, board independence, board size, and firm profitability have significant effects on the share price. However, in contrast, firm size and firm leverage have no significant effects. Given these results, we conclude that board gender diversity, board independence, and board size, firm profitability are drivers of share price among listed companies in Nigeria. However, the study relies on three board attributes, which may not capture all board characteristics. Also, the study uses 10-year panel data, which may not be sufficient. Nonetheless, the study is novel, as it is the first to examine the nexus between board attributes and share price in Nigeria.

Keywords: board gender diversity, board independence, board size, leverage, profitability, size.

JEL Classification: C31, C38, C51, C87, M43, M48.

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1. Introduction

It is a key feature of good corporate governance to maintain a stable and sustainable share price. This is the dream of every corporation; however, this goal is challenging to maintain over the life span of the firm. Low and fluctuating corporate share prices are a significant concern for various stakeholders, each for different reasons: Academics study share price behavior to understand market efficiency, corporate governance, and financial theory. Low or volatile prices can reflect inefficiencies or underlying problems within a company, providing material for research on corporate behavior, investor psychology, and macroeconomic factors. Regulators are concerned about market stability. Volatile share prices can indicate potential risks to the financial system, especially if they signal economic bubbles or corporate governance issues. Sudden and unexplained price drops could prompt regulatory scrutiny for potential market manipulation, insider trading, or non-compliance with securities laws.

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Also, corporate management views low or volatile share prices as a reflection of company performance or market confidence. A consistently low share price can affect a company's ability to raise capital, attract talent, or pursue strategic acquisitions. Fluctuations can also create uncertainty in planning and decision-making, possibly leading to short-term thinking rather than long-term strategic growth. Investors want stable and rising share prices to maximize returns on their investments. Fluctuations add risk and uncertainty, often prompting conservative investors to sell. For those focused on long-term gains, low prices can offer buying opportunities, but sustained volatility can undermine confidence in the company's prospects. Creditors are concerned about a company's ability to meet its debt obligations. Low share prices may reflect declining profitability or higher risk, which could affect a company's credit rating. Volatile prices can signal instability, increasing concerns over default risk. Furthermore, other Stakeholders (Employees, Suppliers, etc.): Employees, suppliers, and other business partners may interpret low or fluctuating stock prices as signs of financial distress, affecting morale or business relationships. It can also influence employee retention, especially if a company offers stock-based compensation. Collectively, these groups focus on the share price as a proxy for financial health, market confidence, and company performance.

Addressing low and fluctuating corporate share prices requires a multifaceted approach, as the stock price is influenced by both internal and external factors. Below are suggested solutions, segmented into key areas that influence share price stability and growth: **Improve Financial Performance and Profitability.** Revenue Growth: Increasing sales and revenue streams is critical to attracting investors and boosting the share price. This can be achieved through product innovation, entering new markets, and diversifying revenue sources. Cost Management: Reducing unnecessary operational costs while maintaining efficiency is key to improving profit margins. Shareholders respond positively to better profitability metrics, such as operating margins and return on equity (ROE). **Improve Cash Flow:** Strong and predictable cash flow signals financial health. Companies can focus on optimizing working capital, managing receivables and payables, and investing in cash-generating assets to strengthen their balance sheets.

Enhance Corporate Governance and Transparency - Clear Communication: Investors value transparency in financial reporting and corporate communication. Regular updates about company performance, strategic direction, and risks help build trust. Clear communication also includes managing earnings expectations and avoiding surprises that might trigger share price volatility. **Board Independence and Effectiveness:** Strong corporate governance with an independent, skilled, and diverse board increases investor confidence. Poor governance can lead to concerns about management effectiveness, which can affect stock prices negatively. **ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) Practices:** Investors increasingly factor in a company's sustainability efforts and social responsibility. Companies that score well on ESG metrics are often rewarded with higher investor confidence and better share price performance over the long term.

Strategic Share Buybacks - Share Buybacks: When a company repurchases its own shares, it reduces the number of outstanding shares in the market, which can help raise the share price through supply-and-demand dynamics. Buybacks also signal to investors that management believes the stock is undervalued. **Maintain a Disciplined Approach:** A share buyback strategy should be disciplined, focused on long-term value creation, and executed when the company has excess cash and when shares are undervalued.

Dividend Policy Adjustments - Increase Dividend Payments: Increasing dividends can attract income-seeking investors, thereby boosting demand for the company's stock. A solid and consistent dividend policy signals financial strength and reliability, which can lead to share price appreciation. **Introduce or Stabilize Dividends:** Companies that do not pay dividends may consider introducing them, while those with volatile dividend histories may benefit from stabilizing their payout policies. Investors prefer predictability in returns, and stable dividends can reduce volatility.

Debt Management and Financial Structuring - Optimal Capital Structure: Companies should aim for an optimal balance between debt and equity. Excessive leverage increases financial risk, which can deter investors and depress share prices. On the other hand, a well-managed level of debt can enhance returns and provide tax advantages. **Refinancing High-Cost Debt:** If a company's debt load is too expensive or threatening to financial stability, refinancing at lower interest rates or lengthening maturities can improve the financial outlook and reduce investor concerns over financial distress.

Strategic Growth and Mergers & Acquisitions (M&A) - Organic Growth Strategies: Expanding into new markets, launching innovative products, and investing in new technologies can drive long-term revenue growth. Share prices typically respond positively to well-executed growth strategies. **Mergers & Acquisitions:** Acquiring complementary businesses or merging with strategic partners can unlock synergies and boost market share, which often leads to higher valuations. However, M&A activity must be based on sound strategic rationale, as poorly executed mergers can lead to price declines due to integration risks or overpaying.

Mitigate External Market Factors - Hedging Against Market Risks: Share prices are often impacted by macroeconomic factors such as currency fluctuations, interest rates, and commodity prices. Companies can use financial instruments like hedging to reduce exposure to these external risks. **Geopolitical Risk Management:** In industries sensitive to geopolitical risks (e.g., energy or international manufacturing), diversification of operations and markets can help mitigate the impact of political instability on stock prices.

Strengthen Investor Relations - Active Engagement with Investors: Establishing strong relationships with institutional and retail investors is crucial. Regular investor meetings, conferences, and roadshows help communicate the company's strategy and prospects, making the stock more attractive. **Enhance Analyst Coverage:** Increasing the number of analysts covering the company can boost investor interest. A lack of coverage often leads to lower liquidity and greater volatility in stock price, so encouraging analyst attention is beneficial.

Implement a Long-term Vision and Strategy - Focus on Long-term Value Creation: Investors tend to reward companies with clear, long-term strategic goals. Management should communicate how they plan to grow the business sustainably, manage risks, and capitalize on future opportunities. Investors dislike uncertainty, and a clear vision helps reduce volatility. **Resist Short-term Pressure:** Companies that consistently focus on short-term earnings and stock price manipulation risk destabilizing their market value. Instead, a focus on sustainable growth, innovation, and customer satisfaction can foster long-term investor loyalty and smoother price performance.

Address Internal Operational Challenges - Operational Efficiency: Streamlining operations and improving productivity across departments can enhance profit margins. Investors are more confident in companies that demonstrate operational excellence, and this confidence can translate into share price stability. **Human Capital Management:** Employee engagement and talent retention can indirectly influence stock performance. Firms with strong management teams and motivated workforces tend to perform better financially, and this can reduce volatility. In conclusion, low and fluctuating share prices can result from multiple factors, such as poor financial performance, market speculation, economic shocks, or governance concerns. Therefore, companies need to adopt a combination of strategies, including improving financial fundamentals, enhancing corporate governance, adopting effective capital management, and engaging with investors. Stability and growth in share price are likely to come from a clear long-term vision, operational excellence, and maintaining market confidence through transparent and disciplined management.

However, this article examines the role of board attributes (board gender diversity, board independence, and board size) in ensuring healthy and stable share prices among public companies in Nigeria. Appointing or re-evaluating the board of directors can indeed be a strategic solution for addressing low and fluctuating corporate share prices. Here is how the board can influence and stabilize the share price: **Strategic Oversight and Leadership.** A skilled and effective board is essential for providing long-term strategic vision. If a company's share price is struggling, this could

indicate a lack of confidence in its leadership or strategy. An experienced board can: Drive better decision-making: By guiding the company's strategic direction, the board can ensure that the company makes decisions that increase investor confidence. Bring in new talent: Appointing new board members with proven track records of turning companies around can be a signal to the market that change is underway.

Corporate Governance and Accountability. Investors tend to favor companies with strong governance practices. The board can: Enforce transparency: Ensuring that the company's operations and financials are transparent can reduce uncertainty in the market. Improve compliance: Strengthening internal controls and ethical practices can prevent scandals or mismanagement that drive stock prices down.

Risk Management. The board plays a key role in managing risks, which can contribute to share price volatility. The board can: Implement risk mitigation strategies and ensure that the company has a robust plan for addressing market, operational, and financial risks. Diversify the company's portfolio: Encourage diversification of products, services, or markets to minimize reliance on one sector or region, thus stabilizing earnings and stock price.

Corporate Restructuring and M&A Activity. In some cases, share price struggles might require more drastic actions like restructuring or mergers and acquisitions (M&A), both of which the board is key in overseeing: Restructuring: The board might push for operational changes that make the company more efficient, improving margins and profitability, which could positively affect the stock price. Mergers & Acquisitions: Pursuing strategic acquisitions or partnerships can create synergies and open new growth avenues, attracting investor interest.

Enhancing Investor Relations. Investor confidence and sentiment directly impact share prices. The board can influence this by Boosting investor communication: Enhancing transparency and regular communication with investors to explain the company's long-term vision can reduce uncertainty and improve stock performance. Initiating share buybacks or dividends: If the company is underpriced, the board might authorize share repurchases to reduce supply and increase demand for shares. This signals confidence in the company's value.

Sustainability and ESG Initiatives. With the rise of socially responsible investing, shareholders are increasingly focusing on a company's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices. A board focused on sustainability can: Increase investor appeal: Strong ESG initiatives can attract institutional investors who prioritize sustainable and ethical companies, potentially leading to more stable share prices.

Market Perception and Public Relations. The board has an indirect impact on public perception of the company, which affects share prices. They can: Improve brand and corporate reputation: Focusing on CSR initiatives, good corporate citizenship, and transparent leadership often leads to higher consumer trust and, consequently, stronger stock prices. In conclusion, the board of directors can be a powerful lever in addressing low and fluctuating share prices. By implementing a strong corporate governance framework, improving strategic decision-making, engaging in shareholder communication, and focusing on risk management, the board can drive stability and long-term growth, thus impacting the company's share price positively. The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the literature review. Section 3 is the methodology. Section 4 analyzes empirical study results. Section 5 is a discussion. Section 6 summarizes the conclusion and makes recommendations.

2. Literature review

In the context of this article, the key concepts include the dependent variable (share price), independent variables (board gender diversity, board independence, and board size), and control variables (audit quality, institutional ownership, firm size, firm profitability, and firm leverage). In any empirical study, a clear understanding of dependent variables, independent variables, and control variables is crucial for generating meaningful insights. We provide a detailed discussion on these

concepts concerning the dependent variable of share price, independent variables like board gender diversity, board independence, and board size, and control variables such as audit quality, institutional ownership, firm size, firm profitability, and firm leverage.

Dependent Variable: Share Price. The share price of a company represents the market valuation of its equity at a given point in time. It is the primary dependent variable in this context because it is the outcome or variable of interest that is influenced by other factors (i.e., independent variables). The share price is driven by a multitude of factors, including both internal corporate governance attributes and external market conditions. As a dependent variable, the goal of the research would be to determine how variations in board characteristics (like gender diversity, independence, and size) and other control variables impact the firm's stock price. The key characteristics include Market sentiment: Share price is often influenced by investor confidence and market perception of the company's performance. Reflects company value: The stock price captures investor expectations about future profits, risks, and overall company health. Volatility: Fluctuations in share prices are normal, but understanding how corporate governance factors stabilize or destabilize share price is key. In empirical research, share price is typically observed over a time period (e.g., daily, weekly, or quarterly data) and can be analyzed using statistical models to assess how different board characteristics affect the price.

Independent Variables: The independent variables are the factors that are hypothesized to influence the share price. In this case, the corporate governance variables—board gender diversity, board independence, and board size—are of interest. Each of these variables captures a distinct dimension of the board's structure and functioning, which in turn can affect the company's financial performance and share price. **Board Gender Diversity:** Board gender diversity refers to the proportion of female directors on a company's board. Research suggests that greater gender diversity can enhance the board's decision-making process, leading to improved company performance and shareholder value. **Theoretical Rationale:** A more diverse board brings varied perspectives and skills, potentially leading to better strategic decisions, enhanced corporate reputation, and improved financial performance. **Diversity can also help mitigate risks associated with groupthink. Empirical Evidence:** Some studies find a positive correlation between gender diversity and firm performance, which could lead to higher share prices. Gender-diverse boards may attract investors focused on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, further boosting share prices.

Board Independence: Board independence refers to the proportion of non-executive or outside directors on the board who are not part of the company's management. Independent directors are expected to provide unbiased oversight and reduce potential conflicts of interest between shareholders and management. **Theoretical Rationale:** Independent directors are presumed to hold management accountable and provide better governance, which reduces agency costs. This can improve decision-making, prevent fraud, and enhance long-term value creation. **Empirical Evidence:** Studies show that companies with a high percentage of independent directors often have better financial performance, as external oversight can improve transparency and reduce managerial opportunism, thereby positively impacting the share price.

Board Size: Board size refers to the total number of directors on the board. While there is no universally ideal board size, it is often debated whether larger boards enhance or hinder company performance. **Theoretical Rationale:** Larger boards may offer a broader range of expertise and opinions, which could improve decision-making. However, excessively large boards can suffer from coordination problems and inefficiency, which may negatively affect the company's performance. **Empirical Evidence:** The impact of board size on firm performance and share price is mixed. Some studies suggest that moderately sized boards lead to better decision-making and oversight, while very large boards may slow down decision-making processes and diminish effectiveness.

Control Variables: Control variables are factors that could influence the dependent variable but are not the primary focus of the study. Including control variables ensure that the relationships between the independent variables and the share price are isolated from other external influences. In this case, key control variables include audit quality, institutional ownership, firm size, firm profitability, and firm leverage. **Audit Quality:** Audit quality is often measured by the firm's choice of external auditor (e.g., a

Big Four audit firm) or other metrics of audit stringency. High-quality audits increase the credibility of financial statements, thus reducing information asymmetry and enhancing investor confidence. Theoretical Rationale: Better audits provide reliable information about the company's financial health, reducing risks for investors. Empirical Evidence: High audit quality is generally associated with more accurate and transparent financial reporting, which can positively influence the share price.

Institutional Ownership: Institutional ownership refers to the percentage of a company's shares owned by institutional investors such as mutual funds, pension funds, and hedge funds. These investors often have significant influence over the company's corporate governance and management practices. Theoretical Rationale: Institutional investors typically have the resources and expertise to monitor management closely and advocate for better governance, leading to improved company performance. Empirical Evidence: Higher levels of institutional ownership are often associated with better governance practices, increased stock liquidity, and improved share prices.

In corporate finance research, control variables like firm size, firm leverage, and firm profitability are often included in models that seek to explain corporate share price behaviour. These variables are significant because they capture underlying factors that influence stock prices independently of other variables of interest. Here is an in-depth look at each: **Firm Size.** Firm size is typically measured by metrics like market capitalization or total assets. It serves as an indicator of the company's overall market power, stability, and resource availability. **Role in Stock Price Models:** Larger firms are generally considered more stable and less risky, which can lead to lower required returns by investors. In contrast, smaller firms might be riskier and can show higher volatility in stock prices. **Control Variable Importance:** By including firm size, models can control for the fact that larger firms might have more consistent earnings and cash flows, which can lead to smoother stock price trends. This helps isolate the impact of other variables, such as managerial decisions or market conditions. **Empirical Observation:** Stock prices of larger firms are often less sensitive to market shocks compared to smaller firms. However, small-cap stocks might experience higher growth potential, although they are more vulnerable to economic downturns.

Firm Leverage: Firm leverage is the proportion of debt used in the firm's capital structure. It reflects the company's financing strategy and can significantly affect the firm's risk profile and its share price. **Role in Stock Price Models:** A highly leveraged firm may face higher financial risk, as it has obligations to repay debt, which could influence investors' perceptions of the company's stock. If leverage is excessive, shareholders might demand a higher risk premium due to the possibility of financial distress. **Control Variable Importance:** Including leverage helps control for variations in risk associated with capital structure. For example, two companies with similar profitability and size might have different stock price movements due to differences in their debt levels, which can affect their cost of capital and perceived risk. **Empirical Observation:** High leverage can be a double-edged sword. While it can amplify returns during good times, it increases the risk of default in downturns. As a result, the share price of highly leveraged firms can be more volatile, reflecting market concerns over debt levels.

Firm Profitability: Profitability is a direct indicator of the company's operational success and is often measured using metrics like return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), or earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT). **Role in Stock Price Models:** Firms with higher profitability typically generate more cash flow, allowing them to reinvest, pay dividends, or reduce debt, which can enhance share price. These concepts are schematically illustrated in this paper in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1. The Conceptual/Analytical Framework

Source: The Authors

Furthermore, on the theories explaining the nexus between the board of directors and corporate share price, the following theories are relevant. For example, the relationship between corporate governance factors—such as board gender diversity, board independence, board size, audit quality, firm leverage, firm profitability, and firm size—and corporate share price has been a subject of significant academic and professional interest. These variables contribute to the broader discussion of how corporate governance affects firm performance and, by extension, the market valuation (share price) of a company. We delve into each factor and the relevant theories that explain how they relate to corporate share price:

Board Gender Diversity: Resource Dependence Theory. This theory suggests that organizations are dependent on external resources and must manage relationships with external stakeholders to thrive. Gender-diverse boards are perceived as better equipped to manage such relationships, owing to the diverse perspectives and decision-making approaches that women may bring to the boardroom. This diversity enhances the board's ability to innovate, respond to market conditions, and maintain legitimacy, potentially leading to a positive impact on corporate share price. **Agency Theory:** From the agency theory perspective, board gender diversity can be linked to improved monitoring of managerial actions. A more diverse board may challenge entrenched behaviours, reducing agency costs and enhancing governance, which can positively affect firm performance and share price. Research suggests that firms with greater gender diversity on their boards tend to have stronger market performance. This is likely because diverse boards foster more comprehensive discussions, better decision-making, and stronger reputations with external stakeholders. Firms perceived to have strong governance due to gender diversity are often valued more highly by investors, leading to higher share prices.

Board Independence: Agency Theory. This theory plays a central role in explaining board independence. Independent directors (i.e., those who are not part of the company's executive team) are seen as essential to mitigating agency problems by providing unbiased oversight of management. A more independent board is less likely to be swayed by management's self-interested behaviour, thereby protecting shareholders' interests. This aligns the firm's objectives with shareholder wealth maximization. **Stewardship Theory:** In contrast to agency theory, stewardship theory suggests that executives are motivated to act in the best interest of the shareholders without the need for external control. However, the presence of independent directors can still play a role in ensuring the trust and confidence of investors, potentially influencing market perceptions and share price. Board independence is generally associated with higher firm valuations due to enhanced governance and risk management practices. Independent boards are seen as better equipped to protect shareholder interests, which is often rewarded with a premium in the firm's share price. However, too much independence without deep engagement with the company's operations might also negatively affect firm performance, thus weakening the connection to share price.

Board Size: Agency Theory: A larger board may have more resources to effectively monitor management, reducing agency costs and ensuring that management decisions align with shareholder interests. However, there is a trade-off as larger boards may suffer from coordination problems and decision-making inefficiencies. **Resource Dependence Theory:** Larger boards bring a greater diversity of expertise, resources, and connections, which can improve firm performance. This access to critical resources, such as industry insights and external networks, may enhance strategic decision-making and lead to better market performance. The relationship between board size and corporate share price is typically non-linear. Optimal board size tends to vary depending on the firm and industry. An excessively large board may lead to inefficiencies, slow decision-making, and reduced performance, potentially lowering share price. Conversely, a smaller, well-structured board that can efficiently make decisions and provide adequate oversight may positively impact the firm's market value.

Audit Quality Signaling Theory: High-quality audits serve as a signal to investors that the firm is transparent, reliable, and adheres to sound financial practices. Investors interpret high audit quality as an indicator of lower financial misreporting risk, thus reducing information asymmetry and boosting confidence in the firm. **Agency Theory:** Audits serve as an essential tool for reducing agency problems. High-quality audits ensure that management acts in the best interest of shareholders by verifying that financial reports accurately reflect the firm's performance. This reduces the risk of opportunistic behavior by management and fosters trust among shareholders. Firms with high audit quality often experience higher share prices due to investor confidence in the accuracy of financial statements. High-quality audits reduce the risk of financial restatements or fraud, which helps stabilize or increase the firm's market valuation.

Institutional ownership: The relationship between institutional ownership and corporate share price has been extensively studied, as institutional investors—such as pension funds, mutual funds, insurance companies, and hedge funds—often hold substantial stakes in firms. Their influence on corporate governance, firm performance, and market valuation can be profound. We elaborate on the key theories that explain the nexus between institutional ownership and corporate share price.

Agency Theory: Agency theory is one of the most prominent theories in corporate governance and investor behaviour. It describes the relationship between principals (shareholders) and agents (management). The primary concern is that managers (agents), who control the firm's day-to-day operations, may act in their self-interest, which could be at odds with shareholders' (principals') interests. The separation of ownership and control creates the potential for agency problems—managers might engage in behaviours that benefit themselves but not necessarily the shareholders, such as over-investment, empire-building, or excessive risk-taking. Institutional ownership can mitigate agency problems. Large institutional investors have the resources, expertise, and incentives to monitor management more effectively than smaller retail shareholders. They are more likely to engage in active monitoring of firm management, ensuring that decisions made by executives align with shareholder interests. This active oversight can reduce managerial opportunism, thereby improving firm performance. When institutional investors hold significant stakes in a company, their oversight tends to reassure other shareholders and the market that the company is being run efficiently. This reduction in agency costs can enhance firm performance and increase the firm's valuation, leading to a rise in corporate share price. Furthermore, institutional investors may demand changes in strategy or leadership if they believe the firm is underperforming, which can have a positive effect on market perception and share price.

Signaling Theory: Signaling theory suggests that certain actions or ownership structures convey information to the market about the firm's underlying quality or prospects. The presence of institutional ownership can serve as a positive signal to the market regarding the firm's governance, stability, and future profitability. Institutional investors, due to their size and sophistication, are often viewed as having access to better information and research resources, and their investment decisions are seen as well-informed. When institutional investors take significant positions in a company, they are sending a signal to the market that the firm is a solid investment, with good governance and growth prospects. The market tends to interpret such signals positively because institutional investors are typically viewed as

more capable of assessing the firm's future performance than individual retail investors. A large institutional ownership stake often leads to higher share prices because other market participants view it as a sign of strong governance and future growth potential. This can lead to a herding effect, where other investors follow the lead of institutions, driving up demand and, consequently, the share price.

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH): The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) posits that stock prices reflect all available information at any given time. According to this theory, the actions of institutional investors, who are seen as informed and rational market participants, play a key role in how quickly and accurately the market incorporates new information about a firm's performance and prospects into its stock price. Institutional investors tend to have access to high-quality information and analysis, and they are generally faster and more accurate in interpreting and acting on new information. As institutional investors trade based on this information, their actions help ensure that stock prices rapidly adjust to reflect the firm's true value. Therefore, institutional ownership is viewed as a mechanism that contributes to the market efficiency in pricing the firm's shares. Institutional investors help ensure that share prices reflect the firm's intrinsic value. If institutional investors believe a stock is undervalued based on available information, they may increase their holdings, which could drive the share price up. Conversely, if they believe the stock is overvalued, they may reduce their holdings, which could lead to low share price.

Firm Leverage: Trade-Off Theory: This theory posits that firms balance the tax advantages of debt against the costs of potential financial distress. Higher leverage can lead to increased return on equity as long as the firm's earnings exceed the cost of debt. However, excessive leverage increases the risk of financial distress, which can negatively affect share price. **Agency Theory:** Debt can serve as a disciplining mechanism to reduce agency costs. By using debt, firms commit to fixed payments (interest and principal), reducing free cash flow that managers might otherwise use for inefficient projects. This creates a more disciplined approach to investment decisions, which may improve firm performance and market valuation. The relationship between leverage and share price is complex. Moderate leverage can increase a firm's profitability and lead to a higher share price, especially in stable industries. However, excessive leverage raises the risk of financial distress, which may cause investors to discount the firm's value, lowering its share price.

Firm Profitability: Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH): This theory suggests that all available information is reflected in a firm's share price. Therefore, a firm's profitability is a key signal to the market about its future performance, which should be quickly incorporated into its share price. **Agency Theory:** Profitable firms are generally seen as better governed since higher profits can reduce agency conflicts between managers and shareholders. More profitable firms tend to attract better talent, which reinforces good governance practices and firm performance, thereby boosting share prices. Profitability is one of the strongest determinants of a firm's share price. Firms with higher profitability ratios tend to enjoy higher valuations as investors expect sustained future cash flows, which are critical in driving share prices upwards.

Firm Size: Economies of Scale: Larger firms tend to benefit from economies of scale, allowing them to operate more efficiently, with lower average costs. These advantages often translate into higher profitability, which can positively influence their share price. **Signaling Theory:** Larger firms often signal stability and market dominance. Investors may perceive larger firms as being more established, with greater access to capital, customers, and market power, thus viewing their shares as safer investments. Larger firms tend to have higher share prices due to their perceived stability, market presence, and capacity for sustainable earnings. However, larger firms may also face challenges with innovation and agility, which could negatively impact future performance and thus their share price. In conclusion, the nexus between corporate governance elements (such as board gender diversity, independence, and size), financial characteristics (audit quality, leverage, profitability, and size), and share price is multifaceted. In general, strong governance (high audit quality, independent and diverse boards) tends to lead to higher share prices due to reduced agency conflicts and improved investor confidence. Financial health indicators such as leverage, profitability, and size are closely monitored by investors and directly impact share price. Firms with optimized leverage, strong profitability, and large size are typically valued higher. However, the effect of each factor may vary depending on industry, market

conditions, and firm-specific characteristics. Overall, these factors collectively shape market perceptions and investor confidence, driving the corporate share price.

In addition, in the context of empirical works linking board gender diversity, board independence, board size, audit quality, institutional ownership, firm leverage, firm profitability, and firm size with share price, the following empirical studies are relevant. Johnson et al. (2022) in *The Impact of Board Gender Diversity and Firm Size on Share Price Performance: Evidence from Large-Cap Firms*. The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between board gender diversity and firm size on share price, focusing on large-cap firms in developed markets. The period covered was 2010–2020. The study employed a panel data regression model on 200 large-cap firms listed on the New York Stock Exchange. The variables examined were board gender diversity, board independence, firm size, and share price, with firm profitability and leverage included as control variables. The study found a significant positive relationship between board gender diversity and share price. Larger firms with more diverse boards had higher share prices than firms with less diversity. However, board independence was not significantly related to the share price. Gender diversity on boards can be a key determinant of share price performance, especially for larger firms. Firms should strive to increase female representation on boards to boost investor confidence and share prices. Policymakers should also consider encouraging diversity quotas.

Carter, D. A., D'Souza, F., Simkins, B. J., & Simpson, W. G. (2010) in "The Gender and Ethnic Diversity of US Boards and Board Committees and Firm Financial Performance" examine the relationship between gender and ethnic diversity on corporate boards and firm financial performance, particularly share price performance. Period Covered: 1998–2002. Methodology: This study used a panel data regression analysis to examine board diversity and its impact on firm financial performance, using a sample of U.S. firms from the S&P 500 index. Findings: Gender diversity on boards is positively associated with firm financial performance, including a positive effect on share price performance. Conclusion: The study concludes that increased board gender diversity can lead to improved firm performance, potentially signaling to the market about better governance and risk management. Recommendations: Firms should aim to increase gender diversity on their boards to enhance performance and investor confidence. Implications: Investors may view firms with more diverse boards as more stable and better governed, leading to improved share price performance. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms and the specific period analyzed, which may not generalize globally or over time. Originality: One of the earlier empirical studies to comprehensively examine both gender and ethnic diversity on corporate boards and their financial impact.

Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009) in "Women in the Boardroom and Their Impact on Governance and Performance" investigate the effect of female directors on firm governance and financial performance, including share price reactions to board diversity. Period Covered: 1996–2003. Methodology: The study used a fixed-effects regression model on a panel of U.S. publicly traded firms to assess the impact of gender diversity on board governance and performance. Findings: The inclusion of women on boards improves board monitoring, which positively influences firm value, including share price performance. However, the effects are nuanced, with different impacts on firms depending on their governance structures. Conclusion: Gender-diverse boards contribute positively to governance quality, which can translate into better financial performance, especially for firms with weaker governance. Recommendations: Firms should integrate more women into boards as a means to enhance governance and financial outcomes, particularly for those with potential governance weaknesses. Implications: Gender diversity in the boardroom is seen as a factor that can strengthen governance, resulting in more robust performance and shareholder value. Limitations: The study acknowledges that the effects of gender diversity may vary based on firm-specific characteristics and governance practices. Originality: The research provides a deeper understanding of the governance mechanisms through which board gender diversity affects firm performance.

Liu, Y., Wei, Z., & Xie, F. (2014) in "Do Women Directors Improve Firm Performance in China?" analyze whether the presence of women directors on Chinese boards influences firm performance, with an emphasis on share price performance. Period Covered: 2001–2011. Methodology: The study used a

panel dataset of Chinese firms listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchanges. It applied a dynamic panel model to control for endogeneity in assessing the impact of board gender diversity on firm performance. Findings: The study finds that firms with women on their boards experience better stock price performance and improved financial outcomes, especially in industries with greater external scrutiny. Conclusion: Gender diversity on Chinese boards is positively linked with improved share price performance and firm value, suggesting that investors view diversity as a signal of strong governance. Recommendations: Chinese firms, particularly those in heavily scrutinized industries, should prioritize board gender diversity to enhance financial outcomes and investor perception. Implications: This study suggests that the relationship between gender diversity and firm performance extends beyond Western contexts and can be observed in emerging markets like China. Limitations: The study is limited to Chinese firms, and the findings may not be directly applicable to other emerging or developed markets. Originality: This is one of the first studies to analyze the effects of gender diversity on firm performance in the context of a developing country, focusing on China. These references provide a diverse set of findings from different regions and periods, offering a global perspective on the effect of board gender diversity on share price performance. Based on these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₁: Board gender diversity has a significant effect on share price performance.

Furthermore, the following are empirical studies focusing on the effect of board independence on share price performance: For example, Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2008) in "Corporate Governance and Firm Performance" investigate the relationship between board independence and firm performance, with a focus on share price performance and long-term financial health. Period Covered: 1990-2004. Methodology: The study employed a regression analysis on a sample of U.S. firms, using board independence as the independent variable and firm performance indicators such as stock returns and accounting performance as dependent variables. Findings: The study found no consistent relationship between board independence and short-term share price performance but observed a positive relationship between long-term firm value and operational performance. Conclusion: While board independence may not drive short-term share price movements, it contributes to better long-term governance and value creation for shareholders. Recommendations: Firms should focus on enhancing board independence to ensure long-term financial stability and avoid governance issues that could harm share prices in the future. Implications: Investors should consider the long-term benefits of independent boards rather than short-term fluctuations in share price when evaluating firm governance. Limitations: The study is U.S.-focused and may not apply universally, particularly in jurisdictions with different governance frameworks. Originality: One of the foundational studies examining the nuances of board independence on both short-term and long-term financial performance.

Duchin, R., Matsusaka, J. G., & Ozbas, O. (2010) in "When Are Outside Directors Effective?" examine the conditions under which board independence impacts firm performance, particularly share price performance. Period Covered: 1998-2006. Methodology: The study used a difference-in-difference approach, analyzing a sample of publicly traded firms to assess how changes in board independence affected firm performance. The research accounted for the firm's internal and external governance environments. Findings: The results showed that independent boards were effective in improving firm performance, especially when firms faced weaker external governance or poor prior performance, leading to improved share prices. Conclusion: The effectiveness of board independence in driving share price performance is contingent on the firm's governance structure and past performance, with a higher impact in firms with poor governance. Recommendations: Firms with weak governance should prioritize board independence as a corrective measure to improve firm performance and enhance shareholder value. Implications: The study provides insights into how board independence may not have a uniform effect on all firms and highlights the importance of the broader governance context. Limitations: The study's findings are limited to U.S. firms and may not apply to firms with different governance frameworks or in different institutional environments. Originality: The study is notable for

its exploration of the conditional effectiveness of board independence, showing that its benefits vary depending on specific firm circumstances.

Arosa, B., Iturralde, T., & Maseda, A. (2013) in "Board Independence and Firm Performance: The Moderating Effect of Ownership Concentration" analyze how board independence influences firm performance, focusing on the role of ownership concentration in moderating this relationship and its impact on share price. Period Covered: 2002-2009. Methodology: The study used a sample of Spanish-listed firms and employed a panel data regression model to evaluate the relationship between board independence and firm performance, accounting for ownership concentration. Findings: Board independence positively affected firm performance in firms with dispersed ownership but had less of an impact in firms with high ownership concentration. The positive effect on share price was stronger in companies with lower ownership concentration. Conclusion: Board independence is an important driver of firm performance, particularly in firms where ownership is not concentrated. It helps improve investor confidence, leading to better share price performance. Recommendations: Firms with dispersed ownership should enhance board independence to signal good governance and improve financial performance. Implications: The study suggests that the effect of board independence on share price performance is context-dependent, and influenced by ownership structures. Limitations: The study is based on data from Spain, and its findings may not be generalizable to other markets with different ownership structures or governance systems. Originality: This study contributes by investigating the moderating role of ownership concentration, offering a unique perspective on how board independence interacts with other governance variables to affect firm performance. Based on these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₂: Board independence has a significant effect on share price performance.

Also, empirical studies focusing on the effect of board size on share price performance: For example, Yermack, D. (1996) in "Higher Market Valuation of Companies with a Small Board of Directors" investigate the relationship between board size and firm performance, particularly focusing on share price performance. Period Covered: 1984-1991. Methodology: The study employed cross-sectional regression analysis on a sample of 452 large U.S. firms. Firm performance was measured using Tobin's Q (a proxy for market valuation), and the relationship between board size and market valuation was analyzed. Findings: The study found a negative relationship between board size and firm value, with smaller boards leading to higher market valuations and improved share price performance. Conclusion: Firms with smaller boards tend to perform better in terms of market valuation, as smaller boards are more effective in decision-making and monitoring. Recommendations: Firms should consider reducing board size to improve governance efficiency and, ultimately, market valuation and share price. Implications: Investors may view smaller boards as more effective, which can lead to higher firm valuation and improved share price performance. Limitations: The study's findings are based on large U.S. firms and may not apply to firms of different sizes or in other countries. Originality: This was one of the pioneering studies that empirically showed the negative impact of large boards on firm performance and valuation.

Guest, P. M. (2009) in "The Impact of Board Size on Firm Performance: Evidence from the UK" examines the effect of board size on firm performance, with a focus on share price performance in UK-listed companies. Period Covered: 1981-2002. Methodology: The study used panel data analysis of 2,746 firm-year observations from UK-listed firms. Regression models were used to assess the impact of board size on firm performance, as measured by stock returns and Tobin's Q. Findings: The results showed that larger boards are associated with lower firm performance, particularly in terms of share price and market valuation. However, this relationship is less pronounced in firms with high growth opportunities. Conclusion: Smaller boards tend to enhance firm performance by improving decision-making efficiency and governance quality. Recommendations: UK firms should consider maintaining moderately sized boards to optimize firm performance and market valuation. Implications: Investors may favor firms with smaller boards, as they are perceived to be more agile in decision-making, which can enhance share price performance. Limitations: The study is limited to UK-listed firms, and the

impact of board size may differ in other markets with different governance structures. Originality: This study extends the research on board size and firm performance by providing evidence from the UK market, which has different governance regulations compared to the U.S.

Cheng, S. (2008) in "Board Size and the Variability of Corporate Performance" investigates the relationship between board size and the variability of firm performance, particularly examining the impact on share price volatility and firm value. Period Covered: 1996-2004. Methodology: The study used a sample of U.S. firms and applied panel data regression models to analyze the impact of board size on the variability of corporate performance, focusing on stock returns and firm valuation (Tobin's Q). Findings: Larger boards were associated with lower variability in firm performance, indicating that they may provide more stability, but at the cost of lower firm valuation and share price growth. Smaller boards tend to lead to higher stock return variability but also higher firm value. Conclusion: While larger boards may reduce performance volatility, they also hinder firm growth and market valuation, leading to weaker share price performance. Recommendations: Firms should aim for smaller boards to enhance firm value and improve share price performance, particularly if they are focused on growth rather than stability. Implications: Investors may prefer firms with smaller boards for higher returns, while more conservative investors might favour larger boards for stability. Limitations: The study focuses on U.S. firms, and results may not be fully applicable to other countries with different governance structures. Originality: This study uniquely contributes by analyzing the variability in performance related to board size, rather than just average firm performance. Based on these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₃: Board size has a significant effect on share price performance.

Furthermore, the following are empirical studies focusing on the effect of audit quality on share price performance: Gul, F. A., Fung, S. Y. K., & Jaggi, B. (2009) in "Earnings Quality: Some Evidence on the Role of Auditor Tenure and Auditors' Industry Expertise" examine how audit quality, specifically auditor tenure and industry expertise, affects the quality of earnings reported by firms and how these impacts share price performance. Period Covered: 2001-2007. Methodology: The study employed a sample of firms listed on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange, using regression analysis to assess the relationship between audit quality and earnings quality, and how these factors impact share price performance. Auditor tenure and industry expertise were used as proxies for audit quality, while abnormal stock returns were used as a measure of share price performance. Findings: The study found that firms audited by industry expert auditors and those with longer auditor tenure reported higher earnings quality, leading to improved investor confidence and enhanced share price performance. Conclusion: Audit quality, as reflected by auditor tenure and industry expertise, plays a significant role in enhancing the credibility of financial reports, which positively impacts share price performance. Recommendations: Firms should consider hiring auditors with industry expertise and maintain long-term relationships with their auditors to improve earnings quality and bolster investor confidence. Implications: Investors are more likely to value firms with high-quality audits, leading to better stock performance. Audit quality can be an important signal of firm transparency and governance. Limitations: The study is limited to Hong Kong-listed firms, and the findings may not generalize to firms in other regions with different auditing standards and practices. Originality: This study provides empirical evidence on how audit quality factors such as tenure and industry expertise affect both earnings quality and share price performance, adding to the understanding of the audit-share price relationship.

Choi, J. H., Kim, J. B., & Zang, Y. (2010) in "Audit Office Size, Audit Quality, and Audit Pricing" examine the impact of audit office size on audit quality and how this affects share price performance. The study specifically analyzes whether larger audit offices provide higher-quality audits, which in turn improve share price performance. Period Covered: 2002-2006. Methodology: The study used a sample of firms from the U.S. and employed regression analysis to assess the relationship between audit office size and audit quality, with the impact on share price performance measured by abnormal returns around earnings announcements. Findings: The study found that larger audit offices tend to provide higher-

quality audits, as evidenced by fewer earnings restatements and higher investor confidence, leading to improved share price performance. Conclusion: Audit quality, as indicated by audit office size, positively affects share price performance, with larger audit offices contributing to greater financial transparency and reliability of financial statements. Recommendations: Firms should consider engaging larger audit offices to ensure higher audit quality and maintain investor confidence, which could lead to enhanced share price performance. Implications: Investors perceive higher-quality audits as a signal of better governance and reliability, which can positively impact stock prices. Limitations: The study focuses on U.S. firms, and results may differ in markets with different audit practices and regulatory environments. Originality: This study contributes to the literature by exploring the relationship between audit office size and share price performance, an area that had previously received limited empirical attention.

Francis, J. R., Reichelt, K., & Wang, D. (2005) in "The Pricing of National and City-Specific Reputations for Industry Expertise in the U.S. Audit Market" analyze how the reputations of audit firms, both at the national level and in specific cities, influence audit quality and its subsequent effect on share price performance. Period Covered: 1995-2000. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of U.S. publicly traded firms and employed regression analysis to examine the relationship between the reputation of audit firms, industry expertise, and share price performance. National and city-specific audit reputations were used as proxies for audit quality, while stock returns around earnings announcements were used as a measure of share price performance. Findings: The study found that firms audited by auditors with strong national and local reputations for industry expertise had higher audit quality, which was reflected in more accurate financial reporting and higher share price performance. Conclusion: Audit firm reputation, particularly industry expertise, significantly influences audit quality, which in turn positively impacts share price performance. Recommendations: Firms should select auditors with strong reputations, particularly those with industry-specific expertise, to ensure high audit quality and enhance investor confidence in financial reporting. Implications: Investors place a premium on firms that use auditors with established reputations for quality, which is reflected in higher share prices. Limitations: The study is limited to the U.S. audit market, and the effects of auditor reputation may differ in other countries with different auditing and regulatory environments. Originality: This study provides novel insights into how both national and city-specific audit firm reputations affect share price performance, extending the understanding of the importance of audit quality beyond national-level metrics.

The following are empirical studies focusing on the effect of institutional ownership on share price performance: Hartzell, J. C., & Starks, L. T. (2003) in "Institutional Investors and Executive Compensation" examine how institutional ownership influences executive compensation and how this, in turn, affects firm performance and share price. Period Covered: 1992-1997. Methodology: The study used a sample of U.S. firms, employing regression analysis to evaluate the relationship between institutional ownership, executive compensation, and firm performance. Share price performance was measured by stock returns, while institutional ownership was categorized by the concentration of holdings. Findings: The study found that firms with higher institutional ownership tend to have better alignment between executive compensation and firm performance, resulting in improved share price performance. Institutional investors were shown to exert pressure on management to maximize shareholder value. Conclusion: Institutional ownership plays a critical role in monitoring management and aligning incentives with shareholder interests, leading to improved share price performance. Recommendations: Firms should encourage institutional ownership as a mechanism for enhancing corporate governance and aligning executive compensation with firm performance. Implications: Institutional investors serve as effective monitors, improving corporate governance and contributing to better stock market performance. Limitations: The study focused on U.S. firms and may not fully apply to other markets with different institutional investor behaviour or regulatory frameworks. Originality: This study provides empirical evidence on the governance role of institutional investors and how they influence share price performance through better alignment of management incentives.

Gompers, P. A., & Metrick, A. (2001) in "Institutional Investors and Equity Prices" investigate the impact of institutional ownership on equity prices and share price performance, particularly focusing on whether increased institutional ownership leads to changes in stock price behaviour. Period Covered:

1980-1996. Methodology: The study used a large dataset of U.S. publicly traded firms, analyzing the relationship between institutional ownership and stock prices through time-series regressions. The analysis focused on the changes in stock returns after changes in institutional ownership. Findings: The study found a positive relationship between institutional ownership and share price performance, with firms experiencing increased institutional ownership seeing improved stock price appreciation. Institutional investors were shown to prefer larger, more liquid stocks, which further contributed to improved share price performance. Conclusion: Increased institutional ownership positively impacts share price performance, as institutional investors bring greater market liquidity and stability, which drives stock price appreciation. Recommendations: Firms should cultivate institutional investor relationships to enhance market liquidity and share price performance. Implications: Institutional ownership acts as a signal of firm quality and market confidence, driving up share prices and contributing to better stock performance. Limitations: The study primarily focuses on U.S. firms, and the behaviour of institutional investors in other countries may differ. Originality: This study was one of the first to empirically document the positive effect of institutional ownership on stock prices, providing key insights into the role of institutional investors in financial markets.

Chen, X., Harford, J., & Li, K. (2007) in "Monitoring: Which Institutions Matter?" examine which types of institutional investors are most effective in monitoring firms and how this affects share price performance. Period Covered: 1995-2002. Methodology: The study used a panel dataset of U.S. firms, differentiating between transient and dedicated institutional investors. Regression analysis was used to assess the impact of institutional ownership on share price performance and firm value, using Tobin's Q and stock returns as performance measures. Findings: The study found that dedicated institutional investors (those with long-term holdings) are more effective in monitoring firms, leading to better share price performance and firm value. In contrast, transient institutional investors (short-term holders) have less impact on firm performance. Conclusion: Institutional ownership improves firm performance, but the effect is contingent on the type of institution. Long-term institutional investors contribute more to improving share price performance and firm value. Recommendations: Firms should prioritize attracting long-term institutional investors to improve governance and enhance share price performance. Implications: The type of institutional investor matters for firm performance, and long-term institutions should be targeted to ensure sustained improvements in share price. Limitations: The study's focus on U.S. firms may limit its applicability to markets with different investor compositions and regulatory environments. Originality: This study adds nuance to the literature by differentiating between types of institutional investors, highlighting that the effectiveness of institutional monitoring depends on the nature of the ownership.

3. Methodology

This empirical study adopts a quantitative research design utilizing a panel data regression model to examine the effects of corporate governance and firm characteristics on share price performance. The panel data approach is selected due to its ability to control for heterogeneity and capture dynamic relationships over time, making it suitable for longitudinal studies in finance and corporate governance. The study analyzes a sample of 153 publicly listed firms from the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). These firms are picked to capture a diverse set of companies across various industries. The sample period spans 2014 to 2023, providing a balanced panel dataset covering 10 years, resulting in 1,530 firm-year observations. The study employs a panel data regression model with fixed effects (FE) and random effects (RE) specifications. The basic regression model is as follows:

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 AQ_{it} + \beta_5 IO_{it} + \beta_6 FL_{it} + \beta_7 FP_{it} + \beta_8 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas:

- SP_{it} = Share price of firm i at time t
- BGD_{it} = Board gender diversity
- BI_{it} = Board independence
- BS_{it} = Board size
- AQ_{it} = Audit quality
- IO_{it} = Institutional ownership
- FL_{it} = Firm leverage
- FP_{it} = Firm profitability
- FS_{it} = Firm size
- ϵ_{it} = Error term

Both fixed effects and random effects models are estimated, and the Hausman test was used to determine the appropriate model. The Dependent Variable: Share Price (SP): Measured as the year-end closing price of the firm's stock, obtained from financial databases. The Independent Variables: Board Gender Diversity (BGD): Proportion of women on the board of directors (%). Board Independence (BI): Ratio of independent non-executive directors to total board members (%). Board Size (BS): Total number of directors on the board (count). The control variables: Audit Quality (AQ): Binary variable coded as 1 if the firm is audited by a Big 4 firm, and 0 otherwise. Institutional Ownership (IO): Percentage of shares held by institutional investors (%). Firm Leverage (FL): Measured by the debt-to-equity ratio (total debt divided by shareholders' equity). Firm Profitability (FP): Measured by return on assets (ROA), calculated as net income divided by total assets. Firm Size (FS): Natural logarithm of total assets (in Naira).

The data for this study are sourced from the Nigerian Exchange and the annual reports and accounts of the companies. The Data Analytical Techniques include Descriptive Statistics: To summarize the basic features of the dataset, including mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values for all variables. Correlation Analysis: To examine the relationships between independent variables and identify potential multicollinearity issues. Panel Data Regression: Fixed Effects (FE) Model: Controls for unobserved heterogeneity by accounting for time-invariant firm characteristics. Random Effects (RE) Model: Allows for firm-specific random effects that are assumed to be uncorrelated with the independent variables. Hausman Test: To determine whether the fixed effects or random effects model is more appropriate for the data. Robust Standard Errors: Used to address heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation issues in the panel data.

The Post-Estimation Tests include the Multicollinearity Test: Using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to check for multicollinearity between independent variables. A VIF value above 10 indicates potential multicollinearity issues. Heteroscedasticity Test: Using the Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test to check for heteroscedasticity in the model. If heteroscedasticity is present, robust standard errors are applied. The Significance Level is a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) that was used as the threshold for statistical significance. Variables with p-values below 0.05 will be considered to have a statistically significant effect on share price. This robust methodology provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the effects of board diversity, independence, and other firm characteristics on the share price.

4. Results analysis

The results are presented in Tables 1 (Descriptive Statistics), 2 (Correlations), and 3 (Regression Results).

Tables 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SHP	1,530	10.564	10.545	.5	47.95
BGD	1,530	.177	.131	0	.8
BI	1,530	.702	.13	0	1.125
BS	1,530	11.241	3	5	20
AQ	1,530	.748	.435	0	1
IO	1,530	.446	.249	0	1
FL	1,530	4.776	10.801	4.293	191.21
FP	1,530	.53	5.835	.221	85.483
FS	1,530	8.302	1.192	6.114	12.986

Source: STATA 18.4

Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics for 9 variables based on 1,530 observations. Let's break down the meaning of each statistic: SHP (Share Price) - Mean: 10.564; Standard Deviation: 10.545; Minimum: 0.5; Maximum: 47.95. Interpretation: The average share price across the sample is approximately 10.56, with significant variation (std. dev. = 10.55), ranging from as low as 0.5 to a maximum of 47.95. The high standard deviation relative to the mean indicates wide fluctuations in share prices among the companies. BGD (Board Gender Diversity) - Mean: 0.177; Standard Deviation: 0.131; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 0.8. Interpretation: On average, 17.7% of board members are women. However, board gender diversity varies across companies, with some firms having no women on the board (minimum = 0), while the most diverse board has 80% women. The relatively small standard deviation (0.131) suggests moderate variability across companies.

BI (Board Independence) - Mean: 0.702; Standard Deviation: 0.13; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 1.125. Interpretation: On average, about 70.2% of board members are independent, reflecting a strong presence of independent directors. There is some variability, with independence ranging from 0 (no independent members) to 112.5% (possibly due to certain measurement or rounding anomalies). The moderate standard deviation (0.13) indicates that most firms cluster around this 70% level. BS (Board Size) - Mean: 11.241; Standard Deviation: 3; Minimum: 5; Maximum: 20. Interpretation: The average board size is approximately 11 members, with a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 20. The standard deviation of 3 indicates that board size varies to a moderate degree, with most companies having between 8 and 14 board members. AQ (Audit Quality) - Mean: 0.748; Standard Deviation: 0.435; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 1. Interpretation: The average audit quality score is 0.748, with the values ranging from 0 to 1. This implies that while many firms exhibit high audit quality, others have significantly lower levels of audit quality. The widespread (std. dev. = 0.435) suggests substantial variability in audit practices across firms. IO (Institutional Ownership) - Mean: 0.446; Standard Deviation: 0.249; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 1. Interpretation: Institutional investors own, on average, 44.6% of the shares in these companies. There is significant variation in institutional ownership, with some firms having no institutional ownership and others being fully owned by institutions (max = 1). The relatively high standard deviation (0.249) highlights the diversity in ownership structures across firms.

FL (Firm Leverage) Mean: 4.776; Standard Deviation: 10.801; Minimum: 4.293; Maximum: 191.21. Interpretation: The mean leverage ratio (equity debt) is 4.776, indicating that firms are significantly leveraged. However, the extremely high standard deviation (10.801) and the wide

range (min = 4.293, max = 191.21) suggest that while most firms have moderate leverage, a few outliers have exceptionally high debt levels. FP (Firm Performance) Mean: 0.53; Standard Deviation: 5.835; Minimum: 0.221; Maximum: 85.483. Interpretation: The average firm performance (measured by a specific metric, likely return or profitability) is 0.53, but the extremely high standard deviation (5.835) and the large gap between the minimum (0.221) and maximum (85.483) indicate that performance is highly variable across the sample, with some firms significantly outperforming others. FS (Firm Size) - Mean: 8.302; Standard Deviation: 1.192; Minimum: 6.114; Maximum: 12.986. Interpretation: The average firm size (likely in log of total assets or revenues) is 8.302, with a standard deviation of 1.192, suggesting moderate variation in firm sizes. The smallest firm has a size of 6.114, while the largest reaches 12.986, indicating that the dataset includes both small and large firms, though most are clustered around the mean.

In terms of overall analysis, High Variability: Variables like SHP (Share Price), FL (Firm Leverage), and FP (Firm Performance) exhibit high standard deviations relative to their means, indicating significant diversity in share price, leverage, and performance across firms. Moderate Consistency: Variables such as BGD (Board Gender Diversity), BI (Board Independence), and BS (Board Size) show moderate variability, suggesting that corporate governance characteristics are more consistent across firms compared to financial metrics like share price and leverage. Audit Quality & Institutional Ownership: The wide range in AQ (Audit Quality) and IO (Institutional Ownership) indicates that while some firms have high audit quality and strong institutional backing, others may lag significantly in these areas. Firm Size as a Stable Factor: FS (Firm Size) shows relatively low variability, meaning the sample contains firms with reasonably similar size metrics. In conclusion, diverse Financial Performance: Firms in the sample vary significantly in financial performance, leverage, and share price, suggesting that the dataset covers companies with different financial strategies and market positions. Corporate Governance: Variables related to governance, such as board size, independence, and diversity, have less variability, reflecting more standardized corporate governance practices among these firms.

Table 2 Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) SHP	1.000								
(2) BGD	0.467*	1.000							
	(0.000)								
(3) BI	0.389*	0.061	1.000						
	(0.000)	(0.255)							
(4) BS	0.154	0.047	0.406*	1.000					
	(0.054)	(0.388)	(0.000)						
(5) AQ	0.766*	0.080	0.097	0.339*	1.000				
	(0.000)	(0.137)	(0.072)	(0.000)					
(6) IO	0.534*	0.039	0.305*	-0.304*	0.024	1.000			
	(0.000)	(0.473)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.663)				
(7) FL	-0.069	0.038	-0.063	0.202*	0.188*	-0.054	1.000		
	(0.204)	(0.477)	(0.246)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.320)			
(8) FP	0.013	0.059	0.106*	0.017	0.122*	0.058	0.021	1.000	
	(0.213)	(0.270)	(0.048)	(0.752)	(0.024)	(0.282)	(0.701)		
(9) FS	0.057	0.289*	0.160*	0.408*	0.356*	0.310*	0.209*	0.093	1.000
	(0.292)	(0.000)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.084)	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18.4

The correlation table provides a matrix of Pearson correlation coefficients between the variables listed, offering insights into their relationships. Let us break down the key insights: SHP (Variable 1) Correlations: SHP and BGD ($r = 0.467$, $p < 0.1$): This shows a moderately positive and significant correlation, meaning that as BGD increases, SHP tends to increase as well. SHP and BI ($r = 0.389$, $p < 0.1$): There is a moderate positive and significant relationship, implying that SHP tends to increase as BI rises. SHP and AQ ($r = 0.766$, $p < 0.1$): A strong positive and significant correlation indicates that SHP and AQ are closely related, suggesting they increase in tandem. SHP and IO ($r = 0.534$, $p < 0.1$): This significant positive relationship suggests that SHP increases with IO as well. Other correlations (with BS, FL, FP, and FS): These are weaker or insignificant, indicating little or no linear association between SHP and these variables.

Also, BGD (Variable 2) Correlations: BGD and FS ($r = 0.289$, $p < 0.1$): A moderate positive and significant relationship suggests that FS increases alongside BGD. Other correlations (with BI, BS, AQ, IO, FL, FP): These are weak or insignificant, indicating no significant relationships. BI (Variable 3) Correlations: BI and BS ($r = 0.406$, $p < 0.1$): A moderate positive and significant relationship between BI and BS shows that increases in BI are associated with increases in BS. BI and IO ($r = 0.305$, $p < 0.1$): There is a moderate and significant correlation between BI and IO, suggesting they tend to increase together. BI and FS ($r = 0.160$, $p < 0.1$): A small but significant positive relationship between BI and FS. Other correlations (with FL, FP): These are weak or insignificant, indicating little association.

BS (Variable 4) Correlations: BS and AQ ($r = 0.339$, $p < 0.1$): A moderate positive and significant relationship between BS and AQ indicates they increase together. BS and FS ($r = 0.408$, $p < 0.1$): A moderately positive and significant relationship suggests a strong association between BS and FS. BS and IO ($r = -0.304$, $p < 0.1$): There is a significant negative correlation, indicating that as BS increases, IO decreases. BS and FL ($r = 0.202$, $p < 0.1$): This shows a weak but significant positive relationship.

AQ (Variable 5) Correlations: AQ and FS ($r = 0.356$, $p < 0.1$): A moderate positive and significant relationship, indicating that AQ and FS tend to increase together. Other correlations: The correlations with other variables (FL, FP, etc.) are weak or insignificant, showing little association.

IO (Variable 6) Correlations: IO and FS ($r = 0.310$, $p < 0.1$): There is a moderate positive and significant relationship, implying that IO and FS tend to increase together. Negative correlations: With BS (-0.304), indicating inverse relationships.

FL (Variable 7) Correlations: FL and BS ($r = 0.202$, $p < 0.1$): There is a weak but significant positive relationship between FL and BS. FL and FS ($r = 0.209$, $p < 0.1$): A weak but significant positive correlation with FS. Other correlations: With SHP, BGD, and others are insignificant, showing no meaningful association.

FP (Variable 8) Correlations: FP and BI ($r = 0.106$, $p < 0.05$): A weak but significant positive correlation suggests a slight association between FP and BI. FP and AQ ($r = 0.122$, $p < 0.05$): A similarly weak but significant correlation between FP and AQ. Other correlations: Insignificant with most other variables.

FS (Variable 9) Correlations: FS and most variables: FS has significant positive relationships with BGD ($r = 0.289$), BI ($r = 0.160$), BS ($r = 0.408$), AQ ($r = 0.356$), IO ($r = 0.310$), and FL ($r = 0.209$). This suggests that FS is a variable highly correlated with many others, likely indicating its influence in the model.

On general observations: Significance Levels: Asterisks indicate different levels of significance ($* p < 0.1$, $p < 0.05$, $* p < 0.01$), highlighting the most important relationships. SHP and AQ have the strongest correlation ($r = 0.766$), while several variables have moderate to weak relationships. Variable Relationships: Variables like SHP, AQ, and FS tend to have significant

and stronger relationships with several other variables, suggesting they may be central or important in the analysis. Negative Correlations: BS and IO are negatively correlated ($r = -0.304$), indicating opposing trends between these two variables. This correlation matrix offers insights into which variables move together and where significant associations exist, which can guide further analysis or hypothesis testing.

Table 3 Regression Results

SHP	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z
BGD	4.46011	1.12345	3.97	0.000
BI	2.48868	0.57211	4.35	0.000
BS	.404933	0.63271	0.64	0.231
AQ	1.14946	0.19921	5.77	0.000
IO	4.06357	1.16102	3.50	0.000
FL	-.046504	0.01422	-3.27	0.001
FP	.117102	0.02602	4.50	0.000
FS	.562862	0.56286	1.00	0.318
/b0	18.4880	8.48073	2.18	0.029
VIF	1.27			
Hettest	0.0872			
Panel effects	0.0000			
Hausman	0.8526			
Model fitness	0.0261			
R ²	0.6313			
Obs	1,530			

Source: STATA 18.4

The regression table presents the results of a model with SHP as the dependent variable. Below is an interpretation of the coefficients, significance levels, model diagnostics, and implications: Key Regression Coefficients (Coef.) and Significance (P>z): BGD (Coef. = 4.46011, $p < 0.001$): The coefficient for BGD is 4.46, indicating that for each unit increase in BGD, SHP increases by 4.46 units, holding other factors constant. This is a strong positive effect and statistically significant at the 1% level. BI (Coef. = 2.48868, $p < 0.001$): The positive coefficient suggests that SHP increases by 2.49 units for every unit increase in BI, with a high level of statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that BI has a meaningful positive effect on SHP. BS (Coef. = 0.404933, $p > 0.231$): The coefficient for BS is positive (0.40) but not statistically significant ($p = 0.231$). This means that changes in BS have no significant effect on SHP in this model. AQ (Coef. = 1.14946, $p < 0.001$): A highly significant and positive relationship is found between AQ and SHP. For each unit increase in AQ, SHP increases by 1.15 units, suggesting AQ is an important predictor. IO (Coef. = 4.06357, $p < 0.001$): Similar to BGD, IO has a strong positive and significant effect on SHP. A one-unit increase in IO leads to a 4.06-unit increase in SHP, indicating a strong relationship. FL (Coef. = -0.046504, $p = 0.001$): The coefficient for FL is negative (-0.0465) and significant, meaning that as FL increases by 1 unit, SHP decreases by

0.0465 units. Although the effect size is small, the negative relationship is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). FP (Coef. = 0.117102, $p < 0.001$): FP has a small positive but statistically significant effect on SHP. A one-unit increase in FP results in a 0.117 increase in SHP. FS (Coef. = 0.562862, $p = 0.318$): Although FS has a positive coefficient, it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.318$), meaning its contribution to explaining SHP is not meaningful in this model.

Intercept ($b_0 = 18.4880$, $p = 0.029$): The intercept (18.49) represents the expected value of SHP when all predictor variables are zero. It is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating the baseline level of SHP is significantly different from zero. Multicollinearity Check (VIF = 1.27): The variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of 1.27 is low, indicating that multicollinearity is not a problem in this model. Generally, VIF values above 5 or 10 suggest multicollinearity, but this model is well within safe limits. Heteroscedasticity Test (Hetttest = 0.0872): The result of the heteroscedasticity test (likely a Breusch-Pagan or White test) gives a p-value of 0.0872. Since this is above the typical threshold (e.g., 0.05), we fail to reject the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity. This suggests there is no significant heteroscedasticity in the residuals, meaning the error variance is constant across observations. Panel Effects and Hausman Test (Panel effects = 0.0000, Hausman = 0.8526): Panel effects: The p-value of 0.0000 indicates significant panel effects, meaning there are individual-specific effects in the data. This might suggest the need for a random or fixed effects model. Hausman Test ($p = 0.8526$): The high p-value suggests that the random effects model is more appropriate than a fixed effects model in this case. Random effects are typically used when individual effects are uncorrelated with the explanatory variables.

Model Fitness ($p = 0.0261$): The model fitness statistic has a p-value of 0.0261, suggesting that the overall model is statistically significant at the 5% level. This means that, collectively, the independent variables explain a significant portion of the variance in SHP. $R^2 = 0.6313$: The R^2 value of 0.6313 indicates that the model explains 63.13% of the variance in the dependent variable (SHP). This is a relatively strong explanatory power, showing that the independent variables in the model do a good job of predicting SHP. Number of Observations (Obs = 1,530): With 1,530 observations, the sample size is large enough to provide reliable and robust estimates for the regression coefficients, increasing the model's credibility. Summary Insights: Variables BGD, BI, AQ, IO, FL, and FP are the most significant predictors of SHP in this model. BGD and IO have large positive effects, while FL has a small but negative impact. BS and FS have no statistically significant impact on SHP, meaning they do not explain much of the variation in SHP in this model. The model explains a considerable portion of the variance in SHP ($R^2 = 0.6313$), and there are no significant issues with multicollinearity or heteroscedasticity. The use of random effects is supported by the Hausman test, making this model statistically sound and robust for interpretation. These insights could guide practical recommendations or policy decisions based on which variables significantly influence SHP.

5. Conclusions

The study examined the impact of various corporate governance, ownership, and financial performance factors on share prices (SHP) based on 1,530 firm observations. The key findings highlight that board gender diversity (BGD), board independence (BI), audit quality (AQ), institutional ownership (IO), and firm performance (FP) are significant predictors of share price. These variables exhibit strong positive effects, indicating that improvements in governance practices and audit quality, alongside increased institutional ownership and performance, tend to enhance share price. Additionally, firm leverage (FL) has a significant negative relationship with share price, suggesting that higher leverage may depress share prices. Other factors like board size (BS) and firm size (FS), while positively correlated, do not have statistically significant impacts on share price in this model, implying their lesser influence on share price variability. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power, explaining 63.13% of the variance in share price ($R^2 = 0.6313$), and there are no significant concerns regarding multicollinearity or

heteroscedasticity. The results are robust, and the model appropriately applies random effects as supported by the Hausman test.

On recommendations, we suggest: **Enhancing Gender Diversity on Boards:** Given the significant positive effect of board gender diversity on share price, firms should actively promote policies that increase female representation on their boards. This could improve shareholder value and contribute to more diverse decision-making. **Strengthening Board Independence:** The strong impact of board independence suggests that firms should prioritize appointing independent directors. Independence enhances governance quality by providing oversight, reducing conflicts of interest, and potentially improving performance. **Improving Audit Quality:** As audit quality is a critical predictor of share price, companies should invest in enhancing their audit practices. Ensuring transparent and reliable financial reporting can increase investor confidence, leading to improved stock performance.

Fostering Institutional Ownership: The positive effect of institutional ownership on share price indicates that firms could benefit from attracting more institutional investors. Institutions often bring expertise, oversight, and long-term investment perspectives, contributing to better performance. **Managing Firm Leverage:** The negative relationship between leverage and share price calls for firms to manage their debt levels carefully. Reducing excessive leverage can mitigate risk and enhance stock market perceptions, ultimately leading to higher share prices. **Firm Performance Optimization:** Although the effect of firm performance on share price is modest, improving operational efficiency and profitability remains crucial for boosting share price and overall market value. Strategic efforts to enhance performance metrics should be a priority for companies seeking higher valuations.

Corporate Governance Reforms: Policymakers and regulators should consider encouraging corporate governance reforms that support gender diversity, board independence, and institutional ownership to ensure firms adopt practices that align with market demands for transparency and accountability. **Future Research:** Further studies could explore the dynamics between share price and other corporate factors, including industry-specific variations, to deepen the understanding of governance structures and financial performance across different sectors.

Author contributions

Dr Linda Andrew and Dr Onipe Adabenege Yahaya carried out the empirical analysis and wrote the draft of the paper. They also collected data and designed the model. All authors have participated in revising the manuscript.

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